

A selection of the literature published on the application of net monetary benefit in the procurement of medical devices

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In the field of applications of cost-effectiveness techniques, the medical device sector has been characterized in recent years by the development of the net monetary benefit (NMB) technique, which has proved to be particularly suitable for use in quality-price tenders on devices, especially those of high technology.

Since the literature on this subject is fragmented and difficult to find, this preprint presents a number of references from the international literature (in English language) and from the national literature in Italian language.

Articles published in international journals (English language)

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Articles published in national journals (Italian language)

1. Trippoli S. L'analisi costo-efficacia come base per il procurement dei dispositivi medici. **Recenti Progressi in Medicina** 2017 Sep;108(9):374-378. doi: 10.1701/2745.27989, available at <http://www.osservatorioinnovazione.net/papers/rpm2017.pdf>
2. Messori A, Trippoli S, Bartoli L, Ferracane E. Principali metodologie per incorporare l'efficacia clinica nel percorso di acquisto dei dispositivi medici- ESTAR 3 Minuti, Numero 32, Dicembre 2020, indirizzo web: <https://www.estar.toscana.it/attachments/article/7823/e3m-32%20dicembre%202020.pdf>
3. Ministero della Salute. Documento per la stesura dei capitolati di gara per l'acquisizione di dispositivi medici. G.U. Serie Generale , n. 253 del 30 ottobre 2018). Indirizzo web: <https://www.trovanorme.salute.gov.it/norme/dettaglioAtto?id=66367&completo=true>. Accessed: 11 January 2021.
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